

THE ROLE OF THE OIL SECTOR IN ENSURING SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT OF THE ECONOMY OF AZERBAIJAN**Sevinc İbrahimova***Associate Professor of Odlar Yurdu University, Baku, Azerbaijan***Mayil Orujov.***Honorary Professor of SMBS (Swiss Montreux Business School),
Odlar Yurdu University, Baku, Azerbaijan***Firuze Rzayeva***Assistant teacher, Odlar Yurdu University, Baku, Azerbaijan***Abstract**

The article reveals the role of the oil sector in the economic development of Azerbaijan. An analysis of the directions of the influence of the oil sector on the sustainable development of the national economy of Azerbaijan is carried out, an assessment is given of the dynamics of investments in the country's economy, the country's GDP, a connection is revealed between the growth of investments and economic growth, etc.

Keywords: oil industry, oil sector, sustainable development, investments, foreign direct investment, domestic investments, gross domestic product, sustainable development, economic growth.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The relevance of conducting research related to the issues of the oil sector of the economy in modern economic theory still remains unchanged. The oil industry of Azerbaijan developed rapidly in the 20th century. Powerful production bases and scientific centers were created. One of the greatest achievements of our country was the discovery and development of oil and gas fields. For the first time in world practice, an oil production platform called "Oil Rocks" was developed, which was considered a unique structure at that time. As a result of targeted measures taken during that period, the oil industry was expanded and its ramified infrastructure was created. In recent years, the most important strategic objectives of the country's oil industry have been achieved. The first international oil agreement on the Azeri-Guneshli-Chirag field, concluded in 1994, reflecting the economic sovereignty of Azerbaijan, laid the foundation for the dynamic development of our economy. The work done since that date is a guarantor of the stable development of the present and future generations of the country. In order to successfully fulfill its function, this sector of the economy must be capable of solving multi-purpose tasks of diversified economic development, which is currently one of the priority tasks of the government of the Republic of Azerbaijan.

PURPOSE OF THE ARTICLE

To identify the features of the influence of the oil sector on the sustainable economic development of Azerbaijan in modern conditions and to prepare recommendations for further improvement of this process, taking into account current challenges.

PRESENTATION OF THE MAIN MATERIAL

Ensuring sustainable and long-term development at the current stage of economic development is a priority for every country in the world. Because without the parameters of sustainable development, it is impossible to solve the existing problems in the country's economy at the macro and micro levels. World experience shows that sustainable development reflects the unity of very important elements of economic activity,

integration, globalization, etc., without which it is impossible to achieve the ultimate goal of economic development. After gaining independence, the economy of Azerbaijan faced such an important task as transformation into a new economic and political system. Transformation into a new system requires new economic thinking, new economic relations, new economic views and approaches, a new style of economic behavior, a new system of economic relations, etc. Through all this, the country must ensure the transition to a new system of property relations, implement the denationalization of property, continue to develop various forms of ownership, such as state, private, joint-stock, mixed, widely introduce small and medium-sized businesses, ensure the social well-being of the population based on market models. It is necessary to prevent monopoly, eliminate excessive exploitation of resources, expand the use of new technologies in the production process, and radically restructure the economy on the basis of progressive advanced world experience. The implementation of these tasks should have contributed to the creation of a dynamic, stable, sustainable economy in the country and provide the basis, the foundation for sustainable development [1, p. 19].

In the first years of the country's transition to a market economy, that is, in the early 1990s, the volume of gross domestic product of the country was not at the required level, unemployment rose to an unprecedented level, employment fell to an unprecedented record low, inflation reached a hyperlevel. With the exception of the oil complex, industrial production fell to a very low level, and the food market depended on imports by 80-85%. To ensure sustainable development, which became the most important priority of economic policy in the country, it was very important to solve all of the above problems. However, to solve these problems, enormous funds were needed. But these funds were not available either in the state budget or from other sources. At that time, the only hope for the country was only one source - foreign investment, and the only area that could attract investors for foreign investment was the oil and gas sector of the country's economy.

Table 1.

Dynamics of investments in the economy of Azerbaijan for the period from 2000 to 2023 (million manat)

Years	Total investment		Foreign investment			Domestic investment		
	Sum	Increase and decrease (in %)	Sum	Increase and decrease (in %)	Specific weight in total volume (in %)	Sum	Increase and decrease (in %)	Specific weight in total volume (in %)
2000	1289,8	-	829,5	-	64,3	460,3	-	35,7
2001	1454,5	112,7	1016,8	122,6	70,0	437,7	95,1	30,0
2002	2718,9	186,9	2172,8	213,7	79,9	546,1	124,8	20,1
2003	4249,3	156,3	3311,0	152,4	77,9	938,3	171,8	22,1
2004	5820,3	136,9	4496,3	135,8	77,2	1324,0	141,1	22,8
2005	6733,4	115,7	4628,5	102,9	68,7	2104,9	158,9	31,3
2006	7415,6	110,1	4514,2	97,5	60,8	2901,4	137,8	39,2
2007	10353,9	139,6	5727,2	126,8	55,3	4626,7	159,5	44,7
2008	13328,0	128,7	5625,8	98,2	42,2	7702,2	166,4	57,8
2009	10475,0	78,6	4395,1	78,2	42,0	6079,9	78,9	58,0
2010	14118,9	134,8	6619,7	150,6	46,8	7499,2	123,3	53,2
2011	17048,8	120,7	6849,8	103,5	40,2	10199,0	136,0	59,8
2012	20251,0	118,8	8102,7	118,3	40,0	12148,3	119,1	60,0
2013	21448,2	105,9	8269,3	102,1	38,5	13178,9	108,5	61,5
2014	21890,6	102,1	9175,6	110,9	41,9	12715,0	96,5	58,1
2015	20057,4	91,6	10998,9	119,8	54,8	9058,5	71,2	45,2
2016	22706,4	113,2	16216,1	147,4	71,4	6490,3	71,6	28,6
2017	24462,5	107,7	15697,3	96,8	64,1	8765,2	135,0	35,9
2018	25877,0	105,8	14002,1	89,2	54,0	11874,9	135,5	46,0
2019	26150,0	101,0	13582,9	97,0	51,9	12568,0	105,8	48,1
2020	22484,0	86,0	10413,2	76,7	46,3	12070,8	96,0	43,7
2021	25313,8	112,6	12751,9	122,5	50,4	12561,9	104,1	49,6
2022	29135,1	115,1	14879,3	142,9	51,1	14225,8	113,2	48,9
2023	32080,9	110,1	14671,2	98,6	45,7	17409,7	122,4	44,3
Bcero	386863,3		198945,6		51,4	187887,7		48,6

Source: the table was compiled by the author based on data from the State Statistics Committee of the Republic of Azerbaijan.

In September 1994, three years after Azerbaijan gained independence, as a result of tense and very difficult negotiations that had been conducted since 1991, the "Contract of the Century" was signed in Baku. Thanks to the signing of this agreement and the implementation of the measures envisaged by this agreement, Azerbaijan entered a new stage of economic development. The importance of this stage was that the "Oil Strategy" and the "Open Doors" policy announced by this agreement laid the foundation for attracting large amounts of international capital to the country in the form of direct and portfolio investments. More than 300 companies from more than 10 leading countries of the world began to operate in our country. In order to jointly develop oil fields, foreign companies and countries interested in cooperation with our country began to invest huge amounts of money in the oil and gas complex. Since 1995, thanks to the investments of foreign investors in the economy of our country, a trend of dynamic development has been formed in it, a stable and sustainable situation has been ensured. Thanks to the acceleration of economic processes, since 2000 the foundation of sustainable and long-term development has been laid in the country, an almost annual growth of macroeconomic indicators is observed. The main reasons for this are associated with the activities carried

out for the development of the oil complex, the oil sector [6, p.139]. Analyzing the data of the State Statistics Committee of Azerbaijan, we see that both foreign and domestic investments play a great role in ensuring the dynamic development of the country's economy.

Analyzing the structure of investments for the period from 2000 to 2023, we see that in 2000-2007 foreign investments prevailed in terms of specific weight, in 2008-2014 - domestic investments, and in 2015-2023 - foreign investments again (see Table 1).

It should be noted that over all the years of foreign investment, including 2007, 80-85% of these investments were directed to the fixed capital of the oil industry. It is for this reason that the oil and gas sector has developed rapidly and, having created favorable conditions for the development of other sectors of the economy, laid the foundations for sustainable development in the country.

During the analyzed period, all parameters ensuring sustainable development of the country were successfully implemented, including sustainable growth of Gross Domestic Product, employment level, dynamic growth of foreign exchange reserves, reduction of unemployment, inflation targeting in accordance with the goals of economic policy, ensuring a constant positive balance of payments and settlement balances of the

country, making the country a reliable and flexible partner in international relations, creating a normally functioning budget of the country, monetary, monetary and credit, financial, customs, insurance, investment, energy system, etc. [3, p. 106].

As can be seen from the data in Table 1, for the period from 2000 to 2023, investments in the amount of 386863.3 million manats were invested in the country's economy. These funds directly contributed to the growth of the gross domestic product produced in the country in the reporting year, and also created conditions for the dynamic development of all sectors of the economy. 51.4% of these investments, i.e. 198945.6 million manats, accounted for foreign investments, and the remaining 48.6% - domestic investments. As can be seen from the data in Table 1, with the exception of only two years - 2009 and 2015, for the entire period from 2000 to 2023 there was a dynamic growth of total investments in the country's economy. Compared with 2000, in 2010 the total volume of investments increased by 10.9 times and reached 14118.9 million manats. Compared with 2010, the level of this indicator in 2023 increased by 2.27 times and reached 32080.9 million manats. The average annual growth for the analyzed period was 110.1%. This level of growth has become one of the most important factors in the dynamic development of the country's economy [3, p. 96]. As can be seen from the table data, in terms of their share in the total investment volume, foreign investment prevailed in 2000-2007. Thus, the level of this indicator by year

was: 64.3% in 2000, 70% in 2001, 79.9% in 2002, 77.9% in 2003, 77.2% in 2004, 68.7% in 2005, 60.8% in 2006 and 55.3% in 2007. Throughout this period, the bulk of foreign investment was directed to fixed capital in the oil sector, which ensured the technical and technological renewal of this sector and ensured its compliance with world standards. The years 2000-2007 are characterized as a period of formation of qualitative parameters of economic development, which allowed the country to create its own foreign exchange reserves. As a result of this, starting from 2008, domestic investments began to prevail in the total volume of investments in the country's economy. Thus, their level in 2008 was 57.8%, in 2009 - 58%, in 2010 - 53.2%, in 2011 - 59.8%, in 2012 - 60%, 2013 - 61.45%, and in 2014 - 58.1%. Already in these years, the formation of the country's own sufficient foreign exchange reserves and the achievement of the necessary level of development of the oil and gas complex led to an increase in domestic investments, and at the same time, their reorientation to other sectors of the economy [6, p. 120].

In order to ensure the dynamic development of the country and the solution of the most important tasks of the economy, with the help of investment policy, the consistent development of strategic sectors of the economy was ensured, a market of competitive investment resources was created, investments were reoriented to priority areas of development, and conditions were created for the favorable development of the private sector.

Table 2.
Dynamics of gross domestic product and investments made in the Republic of Azerbaijan for the period from 2000 to 2023 (million manats)

Years	GDP volume	Change (+:-) in %	Volume of investment	Change (+:-) in %	Share of investments in GDP, in %
2000	4718,1	-	1289,8	-	27,3
2001	5315,6	112,6	1454,5	112,7	27,4
2002	6062,5	114,1	2718,9	186,9	44,8
2003	7146,5	117,9	4249,3	156,3	59,4
2004	8530,2	119,4	5820,3	136,9	68,2
2005	12522,5	146,8	6733,4	115,7	53,7
2006	17746,2	149,7	7415,6	110,1	39,5
2007	28360,5	151,3	10353,9	139,6	36,5
2008	40137,2	141,5	13328,0	128,7	33,2
2009	35601,5	88,7	10457,0	78,6	29,3
2010	42465,0	119,3	14118,9	134,8	33,2
2011	52082,0	122,6	17048,8	120,7	32,7
2012	54743,7	105,1	20251,0	118,8	36,9
2013	58182,0	106,3	21448,2	105,9	36,8
2014	59014,1	101,4	21890,6	102,1	37,1
2015	54380,0	92,0	20057,4	91,6	36,8
2016	60425,2	111,1	22706,4	113,2	37,6
2017	70337,8	116,4	24462,5	107,7	34,8
2018	80092,0	113,8	25877,0	105,8	32,3
2019	81681,0	102,0	26150,0	101,0	32,0
2020	72578,1	88,8	22484,0	86,0	31,0
2021	93203,2	128,4	25313,8	112,6	27,2
2022	133972,7	143,7	29135,1	115,1	21,7
2023	123005,5	91,8	32080,9	110,1	26,1
Bcero	1203303,1		386863,3		32,2

Source: the table was compiled by the author based on data from the State Statistics Committee of the Republic of Azerbaijan.

By limiting centralized financing, conditions were created for the implementation of investment opportunities for individual entrepreneurship in the financing of state-owned objects, the implementation of social and infrastructure projects was accelerated, the investment cycle was shortened as much as possible, etc. [3, p. 36].

One of the most important indicators characterizing the provision of dynamic, sustainable development of the country is the dynamics of the gross domestic product (see Table 2).

As can be seen from the data in Table 2, during the analyzed period, i.e. from 2000 to 2023, with the exception of 2009 and 2015, throughout all other years, the country experienced GDP growth dynamics. Compared with the same indicator in 2000, in 2023 this indicator increased by 26.1 times.

As a result of ensuring dynamic development, from 2000 to the end of 2008, GDP increased by 8.5 times and amounted to 40137.2 million manats. As a result of the financial crisis that engulfed the global financial system in 2009, the GDP in our country decreased by 4535.7 million manats or 11.3% compared to 2008 and amounted to 35601.5 million manats. However, in subsequent years, the analyzed indicator again showed growing dynamics, increasing by 2014 and amounting to 59014.1 million manats. This is 1.6 times more than the 2009 figure.

As can be seen from the table data, as a result of the global crisis of 2015, due to a fourfold drop in oil prices, the GDP this year amounted to 54380.0 million manats, which compared to 2014 means a decrease of 4634.1 million manats or 8%.

In subsequent years, as a result of the growth dynamics by the end of 2023, the GDP volume increased by 2.26 times compared to 2015. The GDP growth for the analyzed period shows that the country is undergoing a process of sustainable development. Despite the fact that in recent years there has been a sharp drop in world oil prices on the world market, as a result of large-scale diversification in the country, the GDP volume not only did not decrease, but remained stable and increased from year to year [4, pp. 11-13].

Analyzing the GDP growth rate, we see that before 2007, the level of this indicator grew faster. Thus, compared to 2000, its growth this year was 601%. In other periods, such growth was not observed. The main reason for this was the rapid development of the oil sector due to the strong influx of foreign capital into the country's economy at that time, and the boom in economic development observed on this basis.

Analyzing the indicators of Table 2 and taking into account that over 90% of investment, which is the most important factor in the development of the country's economy, is directed to the oil sector, we can say that the oil sector has acted as a key source of sustainable and long-term development. We see that over the years, investments have played a decisive role in the for-

mation of GDP. In 2003 and 2004, the share of investments in GDP was 59.45% and 68.23%, respectively. These are the highest indicators for 2000-2023. In general, the analyzed indicator for this period was formed at the level of 35.59%, which is quite a high indicator. As a result of ensuring sustainable and long-term development, political, economic, energy, environmental, currency problems and national security issues of the country have been resolved. Having strengthened its geopolitical and geo-economic positions, our country has become the most reliable participant in global processes and a competitive partner in economic relations with each country.

CONCLUSIONS

After the Republic of Azerbaijan gained independence, ensuring dynamic, sustainable development of the economy became possible as a result of the implementation of multifaceted, deep economic processes in various directions. In general, the country's economy's exit from the crisis, the creation of economic stability, the achievement of a stable, sustainable situation, the creation of a basis, a foundation for sustainable development were realized due to the oil sector. The country's oil sector played a decisive role not only in solving these problems, but also in strengthening the geo-economic and geopolitical position of the country. The development of this sector and the stabilization of the macroeconomic situation in the country due to this direction made it possible to implement sustainable development in the country. Since the oil sector is still the leading sector in the country, the most important problems are solved at both the macro and micro levels with its help and support. At the same time, the country is pursuing a policy of large-scale diversification due to this sector, which ultimately ensures the acceleration of sustainable development.

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